

A Quantitative Study of Oxidation Products of Iodine at the End Points of the Titrations of Mercuric and Silver Salts with Iodine-Iodide Solutions

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A quantitative study of a reaction mechanism in the titration of mercuric or silver salts with iodine-iodide solution under certain conditions has been made, which shows that iodine is oxidised to hypoiodous acid and iodate.

Seal (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 453; *Ind. & News Ed.*, 1955, 18, 209) titrated mercuric chloride with iodine-iodide solution in presence of an excess of NaHCO_3 and titrated silver with iodine-iodide solution in sodium acetate buffer medium and developed empirical methods of estimating mercury and silver respectively. The present paper describes the mechanism of apparently complicated reactions of iodine-iodide solution with mercuric or silver salts in the titration.

In presence of NaHCO_3 or in sodium acetate buffer medium, mercuric or silver ions react with iodine with the formation of unstable hypoiodous acid:

But the HIO being unstable decomposes to HIO_3 and the regenerated HI further reacts with mercuric or silver ions:

Note 1: $\text{Meq}^+ = \text{Ag}^+$ or $1/2 \text{Hg}^{2+}$.

Note 2: Actually HIO_3 is present as NaIO_3 in presence of NaHCO_3 or sodium acetate and an equivalent proportion of CO_2 or acetic acid is liberated.

The reaction of mercuric or silver ions with KI is simple:

Now, experiments reveal that all the hypoiodous acid formed does not completely decompose as shown in reaction (2). At the end point, when all the mercuric or silver ions are precipitated as iodide, a small amount of hypoiodous acid still remains undecomposed. This is decomposed by the KI added during the second titration after the first end point:

In presence of an excess of NaHCO_3 or sodium acetate the alkalinity is so repressed that

this reaction proceeds quantitatively to right hand. The determination of the liberated iodine gives the amount of undecomposed hypoiodous acid. The mercury or silver equivalent to this HIO can be calculated stoichiometrically from equation (1).

After the estimation of HIO, the solution is acidified with hydrochloric acid when fresh iodine is liberated by the decomposition of NaIO_3 :

The amount of NaIO_3 is estimated by titrating this iodine. The mercury or silver equivalent to NaIO_3 is calculated stoichiometrically from equation (3).

In presence of NaHCO_3 , iodate cannot be estimated quantitatively as CO_2 carries with it a portion of iodine. But it can be estimated in presence of sodium acetate. When NaHCO_3 is used, the amount of NaIO_3 formed is calculated indirectly by deducting the iodine liberated by HIO from the total iodine consumed in the titration of mercuric or silver ions.

As a known amount of KI is taken in the reagent solution, the mercury or silver equivalent to it can be calculated from equation (4).

EXPERIMENTAL

Mercuric chloride solutions were prepared by weighing chemically pure salt (the purity checked by the standard gravimetric method) and dissolving in water. Mercuric nitrate, sulphate, and acetate solutions were obtained by dissolving pure mercuric oxide (the purity checked by the thiocyanate method) respectively in the requisite amount of nitric, sulphuric, and acetic acid and diluting with water. Silver solution was prepared by weighing silver nitrate (A.R.) and dissolving it in water.

Potassium iodide of Merck's G. R. quality (the purity checked by Volhard's method), sodium acetate of B. D. H. pure quality, and NaHCO_3 of Merck's extra pure quality were used.

Determination of IO^- and IO_3^- at the End Point of Titration of HgCl_2 with $\text{KI}-\text{I}_2$ Solution and Calculation of Hg therefrom

(a) *When Sodium Acetate Buffer is used.*—(i). To a neutral mercuric chloride solution (8 to 25 mg. Hg in 75 c.c.), taken in a 250 c.c. conical flask, a 20% sodium acetate solution (25 c.c.) was added. The solution was titrated with $N/50$ iodine (KI content 4.0g./litre) as usual to the first definite starch-iodide end point. Immediately, potassium iodide (0.5 g. approx.) was added and the liberated iodine was titrated with a standard $N/50$ sodium thiosulphate solution. When the starch-iodide colour just disappeared, HCl (conc., 5-6 c.c. approx.) was added and the freshly liberated iodine was titrated with $N/50$ thiosulphate. The amounts of HIO and NaIO_3 were calculated from the volumes of thiosulphate solution.

(ii). To a mercuric chloride solution (20 to 150 mg. Hg in 150 c.c.) a 20% sodium acetate solution (50 c.c.) was added. For titrations $N/20$ iodine (KI content 10.0 g. per litre) and $N/20$ thiosulphate solution were used. HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) was added for liberation of iodine by iodate.

The results are shown in Table I along with the stoichiometrically calculated values of mercury.

TABLE I
Amounts of HIO and NaIO₃ and their Hg equivalent when Na acetate buffer was used.
 1 Meq. of iodine (converted to HIO $\equiv$ 0.0502 $\times$ 10³ mg. Hg. 1 Meq. of iodine
 (converted to HIO₃) $\equiv$ 0.0836 $\times$ 10³ mg. Hg. 1 Mg. of KI $\equiv$ 0.00422 mg. Hg.

Sl. No.	Hg. present.	Iodine.	Reagent solutions. KI.	HIO.	Iodine equiv. of NaIO ₃ .	HIO.	Hg equivalents of NaIO ₃ .	KI.	Total Hg found.
1.	8.8063 mg.	0.04752 meq.	9.5424 mg.	0.02988 meq.	0.01792 meq.	1.500 mg.	1.498 mg.	5.766 mg.	8.764 mg.
2.	11.0066	0.05842	11.7292	0.03386	0.02590	1.700	2.165	7.087	10.952
3.	44.0263	0.22430	45.9730	0.08375	0.13780	4.204	11.528	27.778	43.510
4.	55.0880	0.27405	56.1610	0.08375	0.18085	4.204	15.955	33.934	54.093
5.	110.0680	0.55050	112.8190	0.11930	0.43710	5.688	36.542	68.167	110.397
6.	184.0920	0.76145	186.0580	0.11575	0.64305	5.811	53.634	94.293	153.938

TABLE II
Amounts of HIO and their Hg equiv. when NaHCO₃ was used.

Sl. No.	Hg Calc.	Iodine.	Reagent solutions. KI	Iodine equiv. of HIO.	Mercuric chloride.	HIO.	Hg equivalents of NaIO ₃ .	KI.	Total Hg found.
1.	44.026 mg.	0.22540 meq.	45.172 mg.	0.0500 meq.	0.0500 meq.	2.510 mg.	14.663 mg.	27.294 mg.	44.467 mg.
2.	55.083	0.28175	56.465	0.0625	0.0625	3.138	18.329	34.117	55.594
3.	110.066	0.54390	109.002	0.0450	0.0450	2.250	41.708	65.861	109.828
1.	54.903	0.27760	56.658	0.0500	Mercuric nitrate.	2.510	19.027	34.234	55.771
2.	68.629	0.34335	70.077	0.0625	Mercuric sulphate.	3.138	23.479	43.342	68.959
3.	137.259	0.67695	138.166	0.0675	Mercuric acetate.	3.380	50.950	83.483	137.822
1.	54.903	0.28003	57.155	0.0675	Mercuric acetate.	4.393	16.097	34.534	55.024
2.	68.629	0.34090	69.580	0.0550	Mercuric acetate.	2.761	23.901	42.043	68.704
3.	137.259	0.66475	135.981	0.0675	Mercuric acetate.	2.887	50.766	81.981	135.634
1.	54.903	0.28245	57.652	0.0753	Mercuric acetate.	3.765	17.343	34.885	55.943
2.	68.629	0.34090	69.580	0.0700	Mercuric acetate.	3.514	22.647	42.043	68.203
3.	137.259	0.67085	136.924	0.0700	Mercuric acetate.	3.514	50.231	82.739	136.477

TABLE III

Amounts of HIO and NaIO₃ and their Ag equiv. when Na acetate buffer was used.
 1 Meq of iodine (converted to HIO) $\equiv$ 0.540 $\times$ 10³ mg. Ag. 1 Meq of iodine
 (converted to HIO₃) $\equiv$ 0.0900 $\times$ 10³ mg. Ag. 1 Mg. of KI $\equiv$ 0.6506 mg. Ag.

Sl. No.	Ag present.	Reagent solutions.		Iodine equivalents of		Ag equivalents of			Total Ag found.
		Iodine.	KI.	HIO.	NaIO ₃ .	HIO.	NaIO ₃ .	KI.	
1.	4.320 mg.	0.02163 meq.	4.43324 mg.	0.01346 meq.	0.00743 meq.	0.727 mg.	0.669 mg.	2.884 mg.	4.280 mg.
2.	5.400	0.02755	5.64592	0.01841	0.00817	0.994	0.735	3.673	5.402
3.	7.560	0.03841	7.87248	0.02287	0.01485	1.235	1.337	5.122	7.694
4.	8.640	0.04132	8.46888	0.02584	0.01609	1.395	1.448	5.510	8.353
5.	10.800	0.05151	10.55628	0.02861	0.02450	1.545	2.205	6.868	10.618
6.	16.200	0.07760	15.9040	0.04474	0.03604	2.416	3.244	10.347	16.007
7.	27.000	0.12852	26.3410	0.05464	0.07672	2.951	6.905	17.137	26.993
8.	54.000	0.24930	51.0916	0.06158	0.19206	3.325	17.285	33.240	53.850

TABLE IV

Amounts of HIO and their Ag equiv. when NaHCO₃ was used.

Sl. No.	Ag. Present.	Reagent solutions.		Iodine equiv. of HIO.	Ag equivalents of			Total Ag found.
		Iodine.	KI		HIO.	NaIO ₃ .	KI.	
1.	10.800 mg.	0.04948 meq.	10.1388 mg.	0.01900 meq.	1.026 mg.	2.743 mg.	6.596 mg.	10.365 mg.
2.	21.600	0.09992	20.4764	0.02574	1.390	6.676	13.322	21.388
3.	27.600	0.12222	25.0488	0.02674	1.444	8.593	16.297	26.334
4.	43.200	0.19400	39.7600	0.02178	1.176	15.500	25.868	42.544
5.	54.000	0.24348	49.8988	0.02906	1.569	19.298	32.464	53.331
6.	75.600	0.33854	69.3812	0.02812	1.518	27.938	45.139	74.595

(b) *When NaHCO₃ buffer is used.*—Immediately after the end point of the titration of mercuric salt solution in presence of an excess of NaHCO₃ with iodine-iodide solution, KI was added and the liberated iodine was titrated with a standard sodium arsenite solution as usual. The iodate equivalent of iodine was then found out by deducting the HIO equivalent of iodine from the total amount of iodine added in the original titration of Hg.

When Hg(NO₃)₂ and HgSO₄ solutions were titrated, sodium chloride (pure, 0.05-0.1 g.) was added before the addition of NaHCO₃ or Na acetate. The results are shown in Table II.

Determination of IO⁻ and IO₃⁻ at the End Point of Titration of AgNO₃ Solution with KI-I₂ Solution and Calculation of Silver therefrom

(c) *When Sodium Acetate Buffer is used.*—To a neutral silver nitrate solution (4.0—10 mg. Ag in 25 c.c.) a 10% sodium acetate solution (25 c.c.) was added and the experiment was carried out as described in clause a(i) using standard solutions of strength *N*/100 instead of *N*/50. For solutions containing 10-50 mg. Ag in 75 c.c., experiment was done as described in clause a (i). The results are shown in Table III along with the stoichiometrically calculated values of Ag.

(d) *When NaHCO₃ Buffer is used.*—To the neutral solution of Ag. (10-75 mg. in 100c.c.) sodium bicarbonate (1-2 g. approx.) instead of sodium acetate was added before titration with iodine-iodide solution and the estimation of HIO was made as usual. The iodate equivalent of iodine was found out by deducting the HIO equivalent of iodine from the amount of iodine originally required in the titration of Ag solution. The results are shown in Table IV.

Effect of the Time taken for Titration

It was observed in duplicate titrations of Hg by the empirical method that the volumes of iodine-iodide solution varied by 2-3 drops depending on the time taken for titration. The reason seems to be that during titration hypoiodous acid formed suffers decomposition and longer is the time taken for titration, greater is the decomposition. The time effect on the titration of mercuric chloride solution in presence of NaHCO₃ is recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Hg (in 200 c.c.)=110.066 mg.

Sl. No.	Iodine-iodide solution.	Time taken for titration.	As ₂ O ₃ soln. (<i>N</i> /20) equiv. to HIO (formed).
1.	10.947 c.c.	50 sec.	1.50 c.c.
2.	10.898	60	1.40
3.	10.824	124	1.00
4.	10.799	157	0.925
5.	10.775	204	0.725
6.	10.750	281	0.725

DISCUSSION

At lower concentrations of the metals, the amounts of HIO formed is more than the amounts of NaIO₃; but as their concentrations rise, the amounts of NaIO₃ are observed more than that of HIO. Evidently NaIO₃ is the decomposition product of HIO.

The reaction mechanism is not changed appreciably in presence of nitrates, sulphates, phosphates, acetates, citrates, and a small amount of chlorides. In presence of NaHCO₃, the chloride content as NaCl should preferably be below 0.25 g./100 c.c. of the test solution and in sodium acetate buffer, it should not be more than that equivalent to Hg. The pH of the test solution is maintained between 7.2 and 8.5 approximately both for mercury and silver. Free CO₂ sometimes brings down the pH of the sodium acetate solution to below 7; it is not desirable when acetate buffer is used for Hg. Hence for an accurate result of Hg in the empirical direct titrimetric method, chlorides, free CO₂, and the pH should be controlled in the test solution as well as in the standardisation. For better end point in the majority of cases, NaHCO₃ is preferable to sodium acetate buffer in the case of Hg. As shown in Tables III and IV, better recovery of Ag is observed with sodium acetate buffer than with NaHCO₃.

Sometimes, on the addition of NaHCO₃ or sodium acetate to the solutions of mercuric compounds, especially nitrate, sulphate, etc., the precipitation of yellow or yellowish red mercury compounds was observed in which case the titration became very slow at a later stage. To overcome this, a small amount of sodium chloride (0.05—0.1g) was added to the test solution. It is also desirable to dilute the test solution of mercuric salt as far as practicable with water before the addition of NaHCO₃ or sodium acetate.

In the empirical method for the evaluation of Hg, the time taken for titration of the test solution and for standardisation should practically be the same, preferably 3 to 4 mins. (cf. Table V).

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